

Government Accounting Harmonization, the case of Mexico, the European Union and Peru

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Abstract: *This research work addresses the Government Accounting Harmonization and its purpose, which is to establish the general criteria of Government Accounting and standardize the issuance of financial information by public entities. The objectives of Accounting Harmonization are: To facilitate decision-making; Homogeneity of financial information; Establishment of norms for the efficient management of public spending; Registration of operations in an automatic, harmonious way, specific to accounting operations, however the advances in Harmonization between Mexico, the European Union and Peru are compared, it should be noted that accountability and international standards are increasingly relevant issues In 2021, a document review method was used and the results that reflect differences between the progress status of Harmonization in each country are contrasted.*

Keywords: Harmonization, Government Accounting, Mexico, European Union and Peru.

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I. Introduction

The General Law of Government Accounting (LGCG). In the first place, it uses the requirements indicated by the National Council for Accounting Harmonization (CONAC) and subsequently the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) are used to evaluate the publication of financial statements (These criteria include aspects on the recording of assets, liabilities, income and expenses, which allow to measure the effectiveness, economy and efficiency in the management of resources. We live in a division into three levels of government of our country (federal, state and municipal), the benefits are sought in terms of having national patrimonial accounting, fighting corruption and inhibiting illegal practices, increasing the efficiency of government management, Strengthen oversight, Improve accountability, An attractive image for national or foreign investors, which will improve the finances of local governments and Facilitate access to credit from financial institutions.

Government accounting is useful for financial information to be useful, it will have to cover the requirements for accountability, oversight and decision-making; In general, it must have the quality of providing the data that serve the purposes of those who use it; in other words, it reasonably satisfies the needs of the different users, —Accounting has evolved since ancient times and is the fundamental nucleus for the growth of companies, to whose sustainability it contributes. Thus, the economic, social, political and cultural development of man has impacted on the advancement of accounting and therefore on its structuring as a system, to provide financial information that can provide useful data for decision-making || (Santos, 2018). High-quality financial information is of great importance, which according to Vázquez and Mora (2016) can generate (...) trust for all users in general, and for potential investors in particular, companies use disclosure as a tool valuable in providing information through the notes to the financial statements ||(p.104).

II. Reflection

1. Does the Accounting Harmonization system achieve a full Accountability in the country?

According to the –NO literature, considering that Mexico has an accounting system that complies with the General Government Accounting Law (Alvarado and J., 2015), this information system has problems in terms of providing timely information. Therefore, there are courses that are called step-by-step Harmonization, this requires certified personnel, continuous improvement training, so we are really in an incipient process that will improve over the years (CONAC, 2009) reported that approximately 70 of those required to account already have the software but almost 90% did not achieve it satisfactorily, because they require a quantity of technical information that requires step-by-step harmonization recommended by (Sanz, 2003), considering that better accountability is expected in month-end closings, cases of insufficient transparency, complicated reviews and economic sanctions and the most critical that I could to become jail.

2. Has Accounting Harmonization been implemented in other countries and has it worked?

Accounting Harmonization has been implemented in other countries, such is the case of the European Union, some of its main activities were the preparation, issuance and validation of accounting standards in the EU, the integration of the Accounting Directive, the management report and its complements, the IFRS in the EU and the entire transition that Harmonization entails, including its collegiate bodies, however, it is the same case considering that the EU for many years was the most important area of logistics activities in the world, the number of accounting operations were and continues to be a feat for civil servants and public servants, it should be noted that they consider the business model and macro trends, so its operation will not be enough due to global changes, I believe that it is working better than in Mexico, its body main is the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG) private non-profit organization, it is important to mention that the EU is the promoter of the fourth industrial and business transformation in which the internet of things is promoted, which is why it is more advanced in terms of Accounting Harmonization with respect to Mexico.

–IFAC establishes 32 IPSAS that contain the highest international reliability accounting practices for structuring quality financial information. These standards include guidelines for the presentation of financial information such as cash flow statements, financial statements and investments, as well as for government information on assets, debt and financial instruments of the public sector (IFAC, 2013). Although IFAC is in charge of developing accounting standards for the public sector, this body does not have the capacity to impose their use. And yet the IPSAS are complied with by several countries (Galera and Bolívar, 2011). Some Latin American examples are Colombia, Costa Rica, Peru and Uruguay (Araya, Caba and López, 2011). In Europe, Spain opted for the use of IPSAS in 2010 as a result of a reform to the general public accounting plan to improve transparency and accountability towards its citizens (Brusca and Montesinos, 2013).

It is recommended that public servants carry out information reviews as presented in figure 1.

Figure 1

Review of content and resources

Note. The figure shows the titles of seven documents suggested for a better understanding of the subject, own elaboration.

III. Methods

Documentary review, abstract logic, questionnaire, expert criteria, it was investigated on Mexico and the European Union and Peru in which the Government Accounting Harmonization has been implemented, it collects information on:

1. The status of Harmonization in the country.

In Mexico, it is in the implementation process according to the articles proposed above.

The European Union (EU) is in a mandatory process for companies that are listed on the stock exchange in Euros.

Peru is in the process of implementation according to the federation of colleges of public accountants of Peru and its board of deans.

2. Description of how it has been implemented.

In Mexico, various agents intervened in the Accounting Harmonization process, among which the following stand out: the Federal Government, the Legislative Power, Superior Audit of the Federation, SHCP / Federative Entities, National Tax Convention (CNH), Association of Control Organizations and Government Control (ASOFIS), Mexican Institute of Public Accountants (IMCP), Mexican Council for the Investigation of Financial Information Standards (CINIF), World Bank / Qualifiers, Permanent Commission of Fiscal Officials (CPFF), Institute for the Technical Development of Public Treasuries (INDETEC) and the (CONAC). –In this Harmonization process, the Directives for accounting and financial information, and the International Financial Information Standards, published in December 2004 by the United Nations (United Nations, 2004), cited by Del Toro (2009) have been carried out. , p. 7), where Harmonization is defined as: -... the decision to maintain the national normative content considering precepts of international standards and supporting the interests of the country's legal and economic sphere"

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The European Union (EU) through its parliament and EFRAG and the processes of planning, review, implementation, improvement, publication.

Peru, through the National Accounting System (SNC), which was modified by the current Law, The SNC is made up of the National Directorate of Public Accounting, which is the governing body of the system, and the Regulatory Accounting Council (CNC), which is the entity in charge of regulating the accounting practice in Peru.

3. Legal framework or regulations and who issues it.

In Mexico National legal framework or regulations was the one addressed by the UV according to (Pacheco, 2016) and the case seen in the article advances in the amount of financial information of the public sector in Mexico as a result of the LGCG, legal regulatory framework international. CONAC, Among the organizations that propose international indicators and standards are the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, the latter with the Public Finance Statistics Manual (MEFP)

The international European Union (EU), issued by the Consultative Group on European Financial Information (European Financial Reporting Advisory Group, EFRAG) of private initiative, Institute of Accounting and Auditing of Accounts (ICAC)

PerúInternacional, issued by the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC)

4. Strengths and weaknesses.

From a SWOT perspective as the acronym of FD, The AMOFHIT is found, which are practically Administration, Marketing, the Human Factor, Information Systems and Technology.

In Mexico

Strengths: Human factor, teamwork and Increase of technological advantages.

Weaknesses: Lack of support from senior management, Evasion of responsibility.

The European Union (EU)

Strengths: Higher level of information in international law than in Spanish, proactive contribution to the work of the International Accounting Standards Committee (IASB). As a result of this convergence process, in August 2005, the IASB issued IFRS 7 Instruments financial information: Disclosure, which replaces IAS 30 and transfers the disclosure requirements contained in both IAS 39 and IAS 32, modifying both and changing the name of the latter to IAS 32 Financial Instruments: Presentation (IFRS Foundation, 2020).

Weaknesses: A good number of matters dealt with by the IAS are not contemplated or are regulated in much less depth in the Spanish legal system. There are also discrepancies in the treatment of specific matters. Consequently, a single accounting regulatory framework has been generated, which is made up of international accounting and financial reporting standards (IAS / IFRS) of the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), designed to be applied in financial statements prepared for information purposes. general. In this regard, Yaguache, Mayancela and Moncayo (2015, p. 279) point out that the IAS / IFRS are: - (...) technical rules that establish the necessary and fair accounting criteria for the valuation, recording and preparation of financial statements with the sole objective that your information is clear and timely, and can be interpreted anywhere in the world ||.

Peru

Strengths: The possibility of rationalizing production processes. In this way, the best utilization of the factors is achieved and with it, the reduction of costs. These procedures should lead to incentivizing competitiveness, improving quality and lowering prices, with direct benefits for consumers.

Weaknesses: The elimination of protection for domestic industries, which may determine in the short term the closure of many of them, unable to face external competition and as a result, the increase in unemployment.

5. Aspects that stand out or make differences with respect to other countries.

Mexico: A University in Mexico, the Universidad Veracruzana (UV), tries to do it, however it does not succeed or at least they did not obtain the expected results.

EU: It is clear that the future of Spanish accounting standardization has to be analyzed within the European harmonizing process, which will result in higher quality economic-financial information and which will have greater credibility and trust by national and international users.

Peru: Consequently, although it is an exogenous phenomenon, globalization brings with it Accounting Harmonization, in addition to its enormous advantages, it also makes the problems of others feel as their own due to the internal instability they generate in these countries, which in turn, volatilizes the growth plans and projections that governments and companies may make.

IV. Results

Mexico: In the case of the UV. By virtue of the fact that it is a law of recent creation and that it is intended to be applied gradually, it was not possible to implement all the developments of computer processes and systems that were needed in one go, since a commitment had not yet been concluded when it was already I had the next one on the doorstep. This form of planning by (CONAC, 2018) has had negative repercussions on compliance by those responsible for carrying out Accounting Harmonization in public entities.

European Union: The first steps towards International Harmonization of the Anglo-Saxon countries have finally led to international standards, those of the IASB, which will constitute the mandatory benchmark for European companies listed in the euro area.

Peru: The generation of a paradigm of the usefulness of financial information has broadened the scope of accounting standards. To the traditional norms of profit measurement, new norms of exposure are now added, incorporated to the same issues, such as the concept of social responsibility and environmental protection.

Table 1 below presents the comparative harmonization table with respect to Mexico, the European Union and Peru.

Table 1

Comparative chart

Status	Description of the current implementation of the accounting Harmonization	Legal framework	Body (s) that regulate Accounting Harmonization	Positive aspects	NegativeAspects	Interesting aspects	Resultsobtained	
Mexico	Implementation	Implementation with self-evaluation, planning, execution, measurement and control processes.	National legal framework	CONAC Among the organizations that propose international indicators and standards are the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund, the latter with the Public Finance Statistics Manual (GFSM)	Human Factor and Technology	Administrati onOrganizati on	A University in Mexico tries it, the Universidad Veracruzana, however it does not succeed or at least they did not obtain the expected results.	Harmonizat ion with areas of opportunity and weaknesses
EuropeanUnion	Obligation	Implementation with processes of self-evaluation, planning, execution, measurement and control, generation of strategies, implementation, parliamentary review, imposition on companies and management, according to Pacheco, C. (2016)	Internatio nal legal framework	Consultative Group on European Financial Information (European Financial Reporting Advisory Group, EFRAG) of private initiative, Institute of Accounting and Auditing of Accounts (ICAC)	Informati onsystems	Administrati onOrganizati on	There is great interest in harmonizing what can be concluded that there are economic benefits.	Harmonizat ion with areas of opportunity
Peru	Implementati on	Implementati on with self-evaluation processes, participatory planning with other member countries of the (IFAC, 2007)	Internatio nal legal framework	International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC)	Human factor	Administrati onplanning	It volatilizes the growth plans and projections that governments and companies can make.	Harmonizat ion with areas for improvement and weaknesses

Note. Own elaboration with data from (Plata, 2016)

V. Conclusion

Progress on the unification of the depreciation system is also encouraging. The Ministry of Finance and Public Credit issues standards —through its Government Accounting Unit and Public Management Reports indicate this (UCGIGP, 2008) and (Rico, 2018) The review of the contents provides us with the documented technical support to respond to the two questions What? And what for? Accounting Harmonization is the process that aims to achieve uniformity between the accounting regulations of different countries. In other words, it consists of an agreement between different nations so that the accounting regulations reach a high degree of homogeneity. Harmonization must be carried out by an international standard-setting body, since we cannot forget that there is not a single nation that has a set of accounting standards with sufficient merits to be adopted by the whole world. At present, the only international accounting standard-setting body is the IASC, which issues the IAS. Always respecting the standardized criteria of the standards, it is possible to arrive at the formulation of perfectly understandable and internationally comparable financial statements, with all the economic, financial, and even political consequences that this implies. The paradigm of the usefulness of financial information has broadened the scope of accounting standards. To the traditional norms of profit measurement, new norms of exposure are now added, incorporated to the same issues, such as the concept of social responsibility and environmental protection.

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